

Regional Analysis of Urban-Rural Differential in Literacy of West Bengal, India

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Abstract

The present paper is an attempt to analyse the changing patterns of literacy and district-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal by using the census data from 1991 to 2011. The study reveals that the total literacy, rural literacy and urban literacy of West Bengal is increasing, and urban-rural differential is decreasing gradually. The study shows that the district-wise distribution of the urban-rural difference in literacy of West Bengal from 1991 to 2011 is not uniform. The study also reveals that urban-rural differential in literacy is low in the south-western and eastern part of the state, while it is comparatively high in the western and northern part due to backwardness in terms of education, urbanization and socio-economic development. The Government should take effective measures to increase the development facility in the backward districts, which will help to decrease the district-level urban-rural differential in literacy.

Keywords: Literacy; Changing pattern; District-level; Urban-rural differential

Introduction

Literacy is a basic indicator of socio-economic development and the most essential prerequisite for individual empowerment. It is considered an important factor of human resource development (Hira & Das, 2018). It enhances the capabilities of individuals and communities in terms of access to health, educational, economic, political and cultural opportunities. Therefore, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 recognized literacy as the basic human right. Literacy is the ability to learn and write with understanding. According to the Census of India, "A person aged seven and above who can both read and write with understanding in any language is treated as literate. A person who can only read but cannot write is not literate" (Ansari & Nasreen, 2014). The urban-rural differential in literacy is one of the vital problems in our country. However, rural literacy has been rising over the last few decades and as a result, the urban-rural differential in literacy is continuously declining. According to census 2011, the total literacy rate of India is 74.0% with the rural areas reporting a literacy rate of 68.9% and the urban areas recording 85.0% literacy, resulting in an absolute urban-rural literacy difference is 16.1%.

Several research works have been carried out on urban-rural literacy differences. In this context, Siddiqui Shafiqullah (Shafiqullah, 2011) conducted an important study on regional analysis of urban-rural differentials in literacy in Uttar Pradesh by using census data of 2011. Mukesh Kumar and Vinay Kumar (Kumar & Kumar, 2012) did a study on spatial patterns and differential in literacy in Haryana. Ghanshyam Prasad Jhariya and C. K. Jain (Jhariya & Jain, 2014) in their article, attempted to study the trends and pattern and their differential of literacy in Madhya Pradesh. Kalyan Sundar Som and R. P. Mishra (Som & Mishra, 2014) attempt to study spatial pattern of literacy and their differential in West Bengal. Baidurya Biswas (Biswas, 2016) also conducted a study on regional disparities pattern of literacy in the rural and urban area of West Bengal by using census data of 2011. B. D. Patil and R. C. Patel (Patil & Patel, 2016) made an in-depth study on urban-rural and urban-rural and male-female literacy of Dhule and Nandurbar districts of Maharashtra. Mridula Pushkarna (Pushkarna, 2017) analyzed the trends and patterns and their differentials of male-female and rural and urban literacy of Punjab. Monika Kaushik (Kaushik, 2018) also did a study on the patterns and their differentials of the rural-urban literacy rate of Punjab.

Few research works have been done on the urban-rural differential in literacy in West Bengal. The present study is an attempt to study the regional analysis of urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal.

Objectives

There are two objectives of the study

1. To examine the changing pattern of literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011.
2. To analysis the district-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal from 1991 to 2011.

Study Area

West Bengal state has been selected as a study area located in the eastern part of India. West Bengal is sharing an international border with Bangladesh, Nepal and Bhutan. It is bounded by Sikkim in the north, Bhutan in the north-east, Assam and Bangladesh in the east, the Bay of Bengal in the south, Odisha in the south-west, Jharkhand and Bihar in the West and Nepal in the north-west. The latitudinal extension of West Bengal is from 21°25' N to 27°13' N and longitudinal extension is from 85°50' E to 89°50' E and the total area is 88752 square kilometres. There are 66 subdivisions, 58 police stations, 341 blocks, 118 municipalities, 3347-gram panchayats and 40218 villages and 924 census towns in the state. The state's total population is 91276115, population density is 1028, and the rural and urban population are 62183113 and 29093002 as per the 2011 census.

Figure 1. Location map

Methodology

The study is based on secondary data, which is obtained from the Census of India (1991-2011). The urban-rural differential in literacy is calculated by using the formula of Krishna and Shyam (1978). Moreover, simple statistical methods are used to calculate the various literacy rate and choropleth maps are prepared by using ArcMap-10.3 to show the district-level distribution patterns of literacy. The formulas for different calculations are as follows:

1. Total Literacy rate = $\{(Total\ literate\ population \div Total\ population\ above\ 6\ years\ age)\} \times 100$
2. Urban literacy rate = $\{(Urban\ literate\ population \div Urban\ population\ above\ 6\ years\ age)\} \times 100$
3. Rural literacy rate = $\{(Rural\ literate\ population \div Rural\ population\ above\ 6\ years\ age)\} \times 100$
4. URLDI = $(ULR - RLR) \div TLR$

Where, URDIR= Urban-rural literacy differential index, ULR= Urban literacy rate, RLR= Rural literacy rate, TLR= Total literacy rate.

Results and Discussions

The present paper is discussed the spatial pattern of literacy in West Bengal. The results of the study have been divided into two parts. The first part is represented the changing pattern of literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011 and the second part is presented the district-level urban-rural differential in literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011.

1. Changing pattern of literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

Table-1 and Figure-2 reveal the changing trend of the total literacy, urban literacy, rural literacy and urban-rural difference of literacy in West Bengal from the census year 1991 to 2011.

Table 1. Literacy rate in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

Year	Literacy (%)				Urban-rural literacy differential index
	Total	Rural	Urban	Urban-rural difference	
1991	57.70	50.50	75.27	24.77	0.429
2001	68.64	63.42	81.25	17.83	0.300
2011	76.26	72.13	84.78	12.65	0.166

Source: Authors' own calculation using Census of India data from 1991 to 2011

Figure 2. Literacy rate in literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

1.1 Changing Pattern of total literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

In 1991, the total literacy rate of West Bengal was 57.70%. In 2001 literacy rate has increased, it was 68.64%. Within ten years, about 10.94% of literacy has increased. In 2011, the total literacy rate was 76.26%. From 2001 to 2011, literacy has increased by 7.62%. Therefore, from 1991 to 2011, the total literacy rate has increased by 18.56%.

1.2 Changing Pattern of rural literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

In 1991, the rural literacy rate of West Bengal was 50.50%. In 2001, the rural literacy rate was 63.42%, so the rural literacy rate has increased 12.92% from 1991 to 2001. In 2011, rural literacy was 72.13%. From 2001 to 2011, rural literacy has increased by 8.71%. So, from 1991 to 2011, the rural literacy rate has increased by 21.63%.

1.3 Changing Pattern of urban literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

In 1991, the urban literacy rate of West Bengal was 75.27%. In 2001, the urban literacy rate was 81.25%, so the urban literacy rate has increased only 5.98% from 1991 to 2001. In 2011, urban literacy was 84.78%. From 2001 to 2011, urban literacy has increased only 3.53%. Therefore, from 1991 to 2011, the urban literacy rate has increased by 9.51%.

1.4 Changing Pattern of urban-rural difference of literacy in West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

In 1991, the urban-rural difference in literacy of West Bengal was 24.77%. In 2001, the urban-rural difference of literacy was 17.83%, so the urban-rural difference of literacy has decreased 6.94% from 1991 to 2001. In 2011, the urban-rural difference in literacy was 12.65%. From 2001 to 2011, the urban-rural difference in literacy has decreased by 5.18%. Consequently, from 1991 to 2011, the urban-rural difference in literacy rate has decreased by 12.12%.

2. District-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal from 1991 to 2011

The urban-rural disparity in literacy is measured by using the value of urban-rural literacy differential index. The district-wise distribution of the urban-rural difference in literacy of West Bengal from 1991 to 2011 is not uniform. It indicates that it varies from one district to another district in the state.

2.1 District-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal, 1991

Table-2, Table-3 and Figure-3 demonstrate the district-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal in the census year 1991. The value of the urban-rural literacy differential index varies from 1.138 in Maldah to 0.146 in Medinipur districts, while the state average is 0.429. The differential index value of nine districts is more than the state average, while six districts are below the state average and only one district's index value is equal to the state average. The value of the urban-rural literacy differential index is highest in Maldah district (1.138) followed by West Dinajpur (1.108), Cooch Behar (0.750), Purulia (0.699), Jalpaiguri (0.696) and Murshidabad (0.660). On the other hand, the differential index is lowest in Medinipur (0.146) followed by Howrah (0.184). The urban-rural literacy differential index is divided into three categories like low (0.100-0.200), moderate (0.201-0.400) and high (0.401 and above). Only two districts fall under the low category, comprising districts are Medinipur and Howrah, which are located in the south-western part of the state. Four districts are under the moderate category like Burdwan, North 24 Parganas, South 24 Parganas and Hoogly, which are mainly located in the middle and south-eastern part of the state. Remain ten districts fall under the high category. These districts are Bankura, Purulia, Darjeeling, Cooch Behar, Maldah, West Dinajpur, Jalpaiguri, Mursidabad, Nadia and Birbhum, which are mainly located in the North Bengal and western part of the state.

Table 2. District wise literacy rate and urban-rural literacy differential index of West Bengal, 1991

Sl. no.	District name	Literacy (%)			Urban-rural literacy differential index
		Total	Rural	Urban	
1	Bankura	52.04	50.01	73.70	0.455
2	Birbhum	48.56	46.60	67.42	0.429
3	Burdwan	61.88	56.83	70.86	0.227
4	Cooch Behar	45.78	42.89	77.23	0.750
5	Darjeeling	57.95	49.17	76.82	0.477
6	Hooghly	66.78	62.29	76.16	0.208
7	Howrah	67.62	61.28	73.72	0.184
8	Jalpaiguri	45.09	39.70	71.07	0.696
9	Kolkata	77.61	-	77.61	-
10	Maldah	35.62	32.57	73.11	1.138
11	Medinipur	69.32	68.27	78.42	0.146
12	Murshidabad	38.28	35.52	60.80	0.660
13	Nadia	52.53	46.06	73.53	0.523
14	North 24 Parganas	66.81	53.36	78.48	0.376
15	Purulia	43.29	40.32	70.58	0.699
16	South 24 Parganas	55.10	52.30	72.02	0.358
17	West Dinajpur	39.29	33.05	76.60	1.108

Source: Authors' own calculation using Census of India data, 1991

*Kolkata district has no rural area

Table 3. District level urban-rural literacy differential index of West Bengal in 1991

Urban-rural differential Index	Categories	Including districts	Total no. of districts
0.100-0.200	Low	Medinipur and Howrah	2
0.201-0.400	Moderate	Burdwan, North 24 parganas, South 24 Parganas and Hoogly	4
0.401 and above	High	Bankura, Purulia, Darjeeling, Cooch Behar, Maldah, West Dinajpur, Jalpaiguri, Mursidabad, Nadia and Birbhum	10

Source: Computed by the authors

Figure 3. District level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal in 1991

2.2 District-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal, 2001

Table-4, Table-5 and Figure-4 show the district-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal in the census year 2001. The value of the urban-rural literacy differential index varies from 0.786 in Uttar Dinajpur to 0.107 in Howrah districts, while the state average is 0.300. The differential index value of five districts is more than the state average, while twelve districts are below the state average. The value of urban-rural literacy differential index is highest in Uttar Dinajpur district (0.786) followed by Maldah (0.627), Purulia (0.399), Dakshin Dinajpur (0.360), Jalpaiguri (0.336) and Cooch Behar (0.315). On the other hand, the differential index is lowest in Howrah (0.107) followed by Medinipur (0.120), Hooghly (0.159), Burdwan (0.165) and South 24 Parganas (0.179). The urban-rural literacy differential index is divided into three categories like low (0.100-0.200), moderate (0.201-0.400) and high (0.401 and above). Five districts fall under the low category comprising districts are Burdwan, Howrah, Hooghly, Medinipur and South 24 Parganas, which are mainly located in the middle and south-east and south-western part of the state. Most of the districts (ten) are under the moderate category like Darjeeling, jalpaiguri, Cooch Behar, Dakshin Dinajpur, Birbhum, Murshidabad, Nadia, North 24 parganas, Purulia, Bankura, which are mainly located in the north, west and eastern part of the state. Remain two districts fall under the high category. These districts are Maldah and Uttar Dinajpur.

Table 4. District wise literacy rate and urban-rural literacy differential index of West Bengal, 2001

Sl. no.	District name	Literacy (%)			Urban-rural literacy differential index
		Total	Rural	Urban	
1	Bankura	63.44	62.04	80.22	0.287
3	Birbhum	61.48	59.88	77.65	0.289
2	Burdwan	70.18	65.83	77.39	0.165
9	Cooch Behar	66.30	64.27	85.18	0.315
4	Dakshin Dinajpur	63.59	60.38	83.28	0.360
5	Darjeeling	71.79	66.00	83.34	0.242
7	Hooghly	75.11	71.02	82.95	0.159
6	Howrah	77.01	72.81	81.02	0.107
8	Jalpaiguri	62.85	58.93	80.02	0.336
10	Kolkata	80.86		80.86	
11	Maldah	50.28	47.76	79.28	0.627
12	Medinipur	74.90	73.95	82.91	0.120
13	Murshidabad	54.35	52.28	68.34	0.295
14	Nadia	66.14	61.82	81.41	0.296
15	North 24 Parganas	78.07	69.07	85.19	0.206
16	Purulia	55.57	53.24	75.40	0.399
17	South 24 Parganas	69.45	67.40	79.84	0.179
18	Uttar Dinajpur	47.89	42.86	80.50	0.786

Source: Authors' own calculation using Census of India data, 2001

* West Dinajpur has been divided into two districts (1992)- North Dinajpur and Dakshin Dinajpur

Table 5. District level urban-rural literacy differential index of West Bengal in 2001

Urban-rural differential Index	Categories	Including districts	Total no. of districts
0.100-0.200	Low	Burdwan, Howrah, Hoogly, Medinipur and South 24 Parganas	5
0.201-0.400	Moderate	Darjeling, jalpaiguri, Cooch Behar, Dakshin Dinajpur, Birbhum, Murshidabad, Nadia, North 24 parganas, Purulia, Bankura	10
0.401 and above	High	Maldah, Uttar Dinajpur	2

Source: Computed by the authors

Figure 4. District level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal in 2001

2.3 District-level urban-rural differential in literacy in West Bengal, 2011

Table-6, Table-7 and Figure-5 reveal the district-level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal in the census year 2011. The value of the urban-rural literacy differential index varies from 0.411 in Uttar Dinajpur to 0.020 in Purba Medinipur districts, while the state average is 0.166. The differential index value of nine districts is more than the state average, while eight districts are below the state average and only one district's index value is equal to the state average. The value of urban-rural literacy differential index is highest in Uttar Dinajpur district (0.411) followed by Maldah (0.279), Dakshin Dinajpur (0.255), Bankura (0.220), Purulia (0.208) and Cooch Behar (0.203). On the other hand, the differential index is lowest in Purba Medinipur (0.020) followed by Howrah (0.063), South 24 Parganas (0.090), Murshidabad (0.098) and Hooghly (0.102). The urban-rural literacy differential index is divided into three categories like low (0.100-0.200), moderate (0.201-0.400) and high (0.401 and above). Twelve districts fall under the low category comprising districts are Darjeling, Jalpaiguri, Murshidabad, Birbhum, Burdwan, Nadia, Howrah, Hoogly, Paschim Medinipur, Purba Medinipur and South 24 Parganas, which is mainly located in the South Bengal and northern part of the state. Five districts are under the moderate category like Cooch Behar, Dakshin Dinajpur, Maldah, Purulia, Bankura, which are mainly located in the middle and south-eastern part of the state. Only one district falls under the high category, which is Uttar Dinajpur district.

Table 6. District wise literacy rate and urban-rural differential index of West Bengal, 2011

Sl. no.	District name	Literacy (%)			Urban-rural literacy differential index
		Total	Rural	Urban	
1	Bankura	70.26	68.93	84.42	0.220
3	Birbhum	70.68	69.10	81.07	0.169
2	Burdwan	76.21	72.65	81.54	0.117
9	Cooch Behar	74.78	73.16	88.36	0.203
4	Dakshin Dinajpur	72.82	70.10	88.68	0.255
5	Darjeeling	79.56	74.27	87.48	0.166
7	Hooghly	81.80	78.53	86.91	0.102
6	Howrah	83.31	79.98	85.21	0.063
8	Jalpaiguri	73.25	69.73	82.39	0.173
10	Kolkata	86.31		86.31	
11	Maldah	61.73	59.37	76.58	0.279
12	Murshidabad	66.59	65.30	71.85	0.098
13	Nadia	74.97	70.85	85.35	0.193
14	North 24 Parganas	84.06	77.37	88.87	0.137
15	Paschim Medinipur	78.00	76.87	85.96	0.117
16	Purba Medinipur	87.02	86.81	88.60	0.020
17	Purulia	64.48	62.73	76.18	0.208
18	South 24 Parganas	77.51	75.68	82.67	0.090
19	Uttar Dinajpur	59.07	55.99	80.28	0.411

Source: Authors' own calculation using Census of India data, 2011

* Medinipur district has been divided into two districts (2002)- Paschim Medinipur and Purba Medinipur

Table 7. District level urban-rural differential index of West Bengal in 2011

Urban-rural differential Index	Categories	Including districts	Total no. of districts
0.100-0.200	Low	Darjeling, Jalpaiguri, Murshidabad, Birbhum, Burdwan, Nadia, Howrah, Hoogly, Paschim Medinipur, Purba Medinipur and South 24 Parganas	12
0.201-0.400	Moderate	Cooch Behar, Dakshin Dinajpur, Maldah, Purulia, Bankura.	5
0.401 and above	High	Uttar Dinajpur	1

Source: Computed by the authors

Figure 5. District level urban-rural differential in literacy of West Bengal in 2011

Conclusion

It may be concluded that the total literacy, urban literacy and rural literacy rate of West Bengal are gradually increasing from 1991 to 2011; consequently, the Urban-rural literacy difference is decreasing. The study shows that there is a wide variation in urban-rural differential in literacy among the districts of West Bengal. It is found that urban-rural differential in literacy is low in the south-western and eastern part of the state, while it is comparatively high in the western and northern part. The statistical analysis reveals that districts with a low urban-rural differential in literacy like Medinipur, Howrah, Hooghly, Burdwan, South 24 Parganas and North 24 Parganas districts are marked by the high degree of literacy rate, educational facilities, urbanization and socio-economic development. On the other hand, a few districts namely Maldah, Uttar Dinajpur, Dakshin Dinajpur, Purulia, Bankura and Cooch Behar district are backward in terms of education, urbanization and socio-economic development. The Government should take effective measures to increase the development facility in the backward districts, which will help to decrease the district-level urban-rural differential in literacy.

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